

An Awareness Program For Rural Mothers About Proper Parenting Of Preschool Children

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Abstract

This study aims to illustrate the effectiveness of an awareness program for rural mothers about the proper parenting methods for their preschool children. The study points out to the importance of creating a sense of awareness among parents in general and mothers in particular about proper parenting methods. It also highlights the concern raised among those in charge of child rearing with regard to making rural mothers familiar with child rearing and providing programs for them. The study sample was composed of (40) rural mothers distributed as follows: (20) mothers make up the control sample whereas the other (20) mothers served as an experimental sample. All of them were housewives with children in the preschool stage. Most of the study population earned an intermediate qualification. Their average age was 25 years. The study revealed the effectiveness of an awareness program for rural mothers about proper parenting methods for their preschool children. Moreover, this program introduced mothers to the wrong methods of parenting and how to replace them with the proper ones. The study also recommended providing educational courses for mothers in kindergartens to identify their mistakes in parenting, allocating sufficient time for mothers to sit with their children along with listening and responding to their concerns. This is in addition to giving more weight to telling a bedtime story, kissing and cuddling before going to bed as being vital. A mother should enjoy parenting as this shall relieve the burden of parenting and she shall feel the joy while parenting and allocating time to play with the child, at least once a week.

Introduction

The first six years of a child's life are crucial in terms of shaping and building their personality. These years are viewed as fundamental and foundational since the subsequent stages of development are built upon. The proper social, sensory, motor, mental, and linguistic counseling provided by the family as well as the kindergarten have positive impacts on forming and shaping the child's personality and his/her normal development in the years to come.

The proper parenting helps produce a generation of children who are well aware of the true meaning of high morals, responsibility, and good social relations with others.

If we ask ourselves who is primarily responsible for the good parenting of our children, the answer will be, without exaggeration, that it is the mother's responsibility in the first place, then the father and the family around them, followed by the nursery, then the kindergarten.

Education requires a lot of effort on the part of the parents, who should allocate more time for the children. The mother is the nucleus of the family, so children since birth are in dire need of the constant presence of the mother around them. This means that when a mother leaves her children at an early age for a babysitter, it is one of the common mistakes that the mother makes without giving heed to the danger of this issue on children. Of course, the babysitter can prepare food for the children, and take care of their hygiene as well. However, what we are after is education; that is, building beliefs and principles, how to make use of free time, and correcting mistakes in a continuous manner without reluctance. This cannot be achieved by the babysitter, so the mother must be around.

But if parents themselves do not strive well in raising their children and bringing them up in a good manner, then the children may become a calamity for them, and a source of their misery in this world and the hereafter. This is due to the fact that all of you are shepherds and each of you is responsible for his flock

The rural environment is considered one of the environments in which the mother is often present around her children, because she has little or no education at all, and therefore mothers in the rural environment do not work but raise their children by nature, that is, as they were raised, and thus many mistakes occur. Therefore, rural mothers need to develop awareness of these mistakes, and proper methods of parenting. According to

Gustafsson, 2012, most rural mothers suffer from symptoms of depression and cruelty by the mother towards her children, as well as the father's cruelty towards the mother.

Based on the above, the current research seeks to enhance the awareness of rural mothers about the proper parenting methods in dealing with their children.

Hence, the research problem can be formulated in the following main question:

The researcher sensed the problem for the following reasons:

The researcher observed the different methods of education in the countryside as the researcher is of rural origin. The researcher found that children are exposed to wrong parenting methods by either hitting or screaming. Weegar, 2018 confirmed that corporal punishment of children by parents has a negative impact on children's readiness for school; screaming and scolding is also considered psychological aggression that also hinders children's readiness to study, especially at early ages. On the other hand, children who are positively raised are found to experience good parenting and lead to differential results. This is what was confirmed by a descriptive study conducted by Barreto, 2018, whose results confirm that there are a set of elements, if available within the family, quality in education will be achieved and positive education is attained, namely: encouraging The child to read and enhance the child's autonomy and self-esteem, as opposed to giving children study or homework burdens that do not suit their ages at all. All of the preceding invoked concern for the researcher and urged her to conduct this research.

The researcher began to search for educational programs or studies that were presented to such a group, and found a dearth of studies within the limits of the researcher's knowledge. There are many programs that help parents with parenting that can be used, such as the electronic parenting program, which is a program that demonstrates the role that technology can play in raising teenage children, as the program is sent to parents by the school by e-mail. The content delivered us made up of articles related to the positive uses of digital media in raising children. Results show the effectiveness of the program in dealing with children and in communicating with the school. This is confirmed by Clarkson, Anne; Zierl, Lori, 2018. As for this category in particular, i.e. rural mothers and providing educational programs for them, it is found that this aspect is characterized by scarcity. This definitely prompted the researcher to conduct this research.

What is the effectiveness of a program for rural mothers to develop their awareness of correct parenting methods for their children from birth to early childhood?

This main question can be broken into the following sub-questions:

1. What are the common mistakes rural mothers make in raising their children?
2. How do rural mothers raise their children correctly?
3. What is the effectiveness of the proposed program?

Research objectives:

1. Rural mothers get familiar with common mistakes in breeding.
2. The teachers know how to present the correct information to mothers in the form of a properly-designed educational capsule that suits their educational, cultural and social level.
3. Preparing an open-question individual interview questionnaire for rural mothers to measure their awareness of proper parenting methods.
4. Designing a program to develop rural mothers' awareness of proper parenting methods.
5. Creating an educational consulting office with educational content for kindergarten teachers to provide advice and guidance to rural mothers when needed.

Significance of the research:

1. Educating parents in general and mothers in particular about proper parenting methods.
2. Satisfying the interest of those in charge of rearing children in terms of educating rural mothers about raising children and offering them awareness-raising programs.
3. The kindergarten administration's keenness to conduct meetings frequently with parents, especially the illiterate, and talking with them about proper parenting methods.

Research Methodology:

The researcher employed the two-group quasi-experimental approach, using the pre and posttest on both the experimental and control groups to verify the validity of the hypotheses and the effectiveness of the program.

Research limitations:

Human limitations: The study sample consisted of (40) mothers divided as follows: (20) rural mothers served as a control sample whereas the other (20) mothers were employed as an experimental sample. All of whom were housewives with children in enrolled in kindergartens; also, most of whom had an intermediate qualification, and their average age was 25 years.

Spatial Boundaries: Mothers of the Mandara Village in Fayoum.

Temporal Boundaries: The study was implemented from July 15th, 2018 until September 15th, 2018 AD. Also, a form was employed as a follow-up measure on 10/15/2018.

Research terms:

Rural woman: a working woman in rural areas, the majority of whom depend on natural resources and agriculture for their livelihood, and they constitute more than a quarter of the world's total population. (United Nations General Assembly, 2012)

Education:

(Education is to teach everyone how to live completely)

A definition by Herbert Spencer (1820-1903)

Childrearing methods:

-Every behavior of the father or the mother or both that affects the child and his personality development (Musa Naguib Musa, 2013, p. 3).

It is the method or method by which parents deal with the child during his life periods from birth to adulthood (Abd al-Karim Mahmoud Salih, 2014, p. 355)

As for the researcher, it is the techniques or methods that parents use during the child's life periods and affect his comprehensive, integrated development.

Research hypotheses

1. There exist statistically significant differences between the mean scores of the research sample for the two groups: control and experimental in the post application in the open-question individual interview questionnaire for rural mothers to measure their awareness of proper parenting methods in favor of the experimental group.
2. There exist statistically significant differences between the mean scores of the experimental group in the two applications (pre and post) in the open-question individual interview questionnaire for rural mothers to measure their awareness of proper parenting methods in favor of the post application.
3. There exist statistically significant differences between the mean scores of rural mothers in the two measures (post and follow-up) for applying the open-question individual interview questionnaire for rural mothers to measure their awareness of proper parenting methods in favor of the follow-up measurement.

Theoretical Framework of the Research

First Axis: Rural Woman

Rural Woman

Throughout the ages, women have been a source of production in their work, whether at home or in economic aspects in their various fields, as they are responsible for raising children and taking care of them as well as being responsible at home along with her role as a mother and wife who does her work outside the house side by side with the man. However, her productive tasks go beyond his tasks, sometimes. This is the case of rural women who are employed in agriculture at rates higher than that of men.

The rural woman wakes up at the break of dawn, prepares the family breakfast, then wakes the husband up as well as the children who find everything they need ready. She helps and prepares family members to leave the house either for study or work, then proceeds with the accelerated pace of her daily tasks. She begins with the house affairs of arranging, cleaning and cooking. Then, she heads towards doing her work that in most cases is in farming as she devotes her time to such a kind of work where she takes care of the land, plants and livestock with the same care that she does towards her offspring.

These are the broad outlines of her daily life program which could portray the image of a rural mother who serves as a housewife and a worker. It is the image of a woman who performs dozens of tasks in one day, as if she has more hands than the rest of humanity. She does the housework and works outside her home to earn her living d outside to gain her strength and help meet the needs of the family. Women in most of the rural areas have the same daily programs with little variation, but it is proven that their day ends with a feeling of satisfaction in performing their duties despite the hardships they experience. (Samah Abbadah, 2015)

Rural women in Arab societies, especially those who fall in poor or middle-income classes, are tasked with domestic work and agricultural work, which are among the most stressful areas of work. In some villages, they are the breadwinners for their families, especially in countries that record high levels of unemployment and poverty. However, such efforts are not well appreciated either physically or morally. According to an article by Walker, 2018, he emphasized that early childhood care goes through highly responsive interactions and learning opportunities. However, only few large-scale programs in low and middle income countries support parents' ability to provide responsive care and activities that assist with children's learning. The Reach-Up Training Program was introduced to promote the capacity of implementing agencies to provide effective parenting programs for children up to 3 years of age.

Although the definition of the countryside is still relative and varied from country to another, it is basically used to refer to the region where agriculture is the basic economic activity. As for the rural woman, it is the woman that resides in the rural milieu, and she is most often practicing farming as a basic activity and sometimes doing small craft or industrial work to secure an income that earns her a decent living.

In such families, men see that a woman's work at home and her concern for the welfare of her children are normal and fall with the scope of her duties and tasks that must be performed reluctance or moaning. It is not

necessary to give her any recognition for such a thing. This ultimately makes rural women not live in luxury, but on the contrary, they shoulder too many burdens which results in psychological distress. According to a study by Murry, 2008, he pointed out the parents' relationship does not entail any luxury and increases psychological distress, especially with rural mothers.

As for agricultural work in its various stages and its different activities such as planting and raising animals, most Arab men do not accept it even on their private ownership. This is what makes the percentage of rural women who work in agriculture exceed that of men. However, this disparity is not exclusive to Arab societies, but rather includes various regions of the world. Based on the results of a study by Gustafsson, 2012, it was found that rural mothers mostly suffer from symptoms of depression and cruelty due to the severe treatment by mothers towards their children, as well as the father's cruelty with the mother.

Perhaps the tendency of women in the countryside to agricultural work has logical explanations associated with the low wages of peasant workers in most Arab countryside, which generates men's reluctance. This could be coupled with the harsh working conditions, long hours, and early rising in the morning.

We also find explanations that fall outside the scope of reason, which is that women are more sensitive, as their emotions are rooted into the land, adore their farms, and feel that they give plants and animals life and nurture them with the same pleasure as caring for their children. The woman is also an example of patience and an incarnation of long breath because the hard agricultural work requires patience while waiting for its outcome. This requires weeks and months sometimes. Therefore, the rural mother must be educated, since she is characterized by herich emotions that should be passed on to her offspring. This has been confirmed by Miller, 2018 who stressed the importance of parents' interest in social and emotional skills in children's success.

Generally speaking, the diversity of activities and work is considered a fundamental feature of women's life in various rural areas, which lack institutional and service facilities such as schools, hospitals and recreational destinations.

On the other hand, the countryside is male-dominated in a strict manner where women are usually productive, yet they occupy an inferior status as subordinates to men. This can be viewed in her inability to get involved in decision-making and managing financial and planning affairs for the family's future. A rural woman follows what the father says without taking into account the respect and appreciation that their children need and the importance of mutual cooperation of both parents in planning the future of children. According to a study by Balsells Bailón, 2018, there are five skills that parents must take into account during parenting, which are adjusting parents' skills in line with children's preferences, considering the needs of the child. Socialization is of paramount importance along with respecting the role of the individual and paying attention to the self-efficacy of parents. All these skills lead to positive parenting.

These burdens, such as the laborious agricultural and household work, that rural women bear, coupled with a lack of appreciation and the inferior status in the family and in society, as well as the disparity between the wages and the effort exerted, have a crystal clear impact on the rural woman's treatment of her children. She does not have the education or the time sufficient to be raised in a proper manner. Furthermore, she does the same thing with her offspring without giving heed to what she is doing or what contemporary parenting means. She does not pay attention to the mistakes she might commit while parenting. Nor does she know that one of her children could be gifted or needs some behavior correction. An article by Sharma, 2018, provides an emphasis on the need to give advice to parents on raising gifted children which starts with giving them the right to choose the school they like and make them free to engage in their favourite non-academic education that develops the talent of the child.

The second axis: Education Methods:

Undoubtedly, the relationship that arises between parents and children is extremely crucial to what the child's personality becomes in the future, as 70% of the child's personality is shaped at preschool age. Parents employ a wide range of methods of parenting, namely:

1. **Authoritativeness:** It is represented by the father or the mother imposing their opinion on the child, and this includes deterring the child's normal or legitimate desires. Parents may use methods that combine both harshness and softness. Such a way eliminates the desires and tendencies of the child from childhood and makes the child's personality usually feel terrified of authority. The child becomes shy, sensitive, incompetent, confused, and insecure. At many times, this is the case, especially when facing situations where there is a choice.
2. **Excessive protection method:** It is that one or both parents perform on behalf of the child the duties or responsibilities that he can perform and that he must be trained in to become an autonomous personality. Such a child develops a weak, fearful, independent personality, dependent on others as it needs to be led and directed. Such types of personalities can be easily misled and fall prey to corruption and conspiracy against their homeland.
3. **Negligence:** It involves leaving the child without reinforcing the proper behavior, as well as without correcting the wrong behavior. This method often results in an anxious and hesitant personality floundering in behavior without clear rules or boundaries. It often tries to join a group or group where it

earns a status and feel successful within it, and finds in it the tender and love that it lacked at its young age. The child has thus lost the social sensitivity within his family, so it is easy for him to break and violate the laws.

Nabil El-Sayed Hassan (2018) highlighted the fact that a negative impact of the virtual electronic environment does exist on positive thinking in children. As parents are busy for most of the time and thus neglect children leaving them for hours in front of electronics. This eventually leads to social isolation and has a negative impact on positive thinking. In case we look forward to making a positive impact out of this virtual environment, parents must practice some positive thinking skills with children such as analysis, inference and evaluation of real situations, which contribute to minimizing the impact of the virtual environment on the child and promoting the child's interaction with the practical reality in which he lives.

4. **Pampering:** It involves encouraging the child to satisfy his desires in the way that pleases him without assuming any responsibility commensurate with the stage of growth he is going through. When such a child grows up, he is found to break his promise and cannot shoulder any responsibility entrusted to him. He is not committed towards his job, but he is dependent on the others who assume top positions or relatives or acquaintances (i.e. favoritism), to reach an objective or position he yearns for.

In this context, Gamal Ali Al-Dahshan (2018) stressed the importance of pursuing after disseminating awareness among parents and teachers in kindergarten institutions on how to invest what technology provides to them and their children to enhance their development and growth. This can be in the form of conducting seminars, workshops and discussion sessions to educate parents, all groups of society ranging from young people and adolescents in conjunction and coordination with some bodies and NGOs, as well as cooperation with business owners. Such seminars should aim to help parents guide their children towards adopting proper use of the information network, and provide them with the latest educational methods that can be utilized at home to deal with digital means in a positive manner. They also should educate them about the negative effects that may result from misuse of such means, and instructing them to engage in family dialogues and discussions with their children. Also, children's questions and inquiries should be answered sensibly and a need to perceive what is going on in their minds such as ideas and information whether true or false is crucial. Knowledge is now available and accessible through the digital space which increases their ability to develop their lives and societies and formulate their decisions and make better choices. The improper use of such tools may lead to negative impacts, which would minimize their role and social effectiveness, as well. Not everything should be accessible or allowable for the child, as he may watch pornographic films or films that contain violence. Therefore, the family must guide and educate instead of agreeing to everything the child requests.

5. **Cruelty:** It is reflected in the use of methods of corporal punishment (beating) and making threats as a basic method in raising a child. This method results in a rebellious personality that tends to aggression directed towards others, such as vandalism without feeling guilty or remorse. Such ill-treated children may resort to torture animals and birds.
6. **Oscillation:** It is represented by the repeated change of both parents in terms of when to use the carrot and stick approach. This is confirmed by Polivanova (2018) who emphasized that modern parents raise their children in a contradictory way. Parents fall into such case through increasing importance placed on career success and family life. Career affects the parents' experiences within the family, and this means that a certain behavior could be a reason for rewarding the child and the same behavior could be a reason for punishment. Contradiction can be seen in parenting behaviours of both the father and the mother. It could be a result of a behavior that both parents find it funny at a time. At another time in the presence of some strangers, it could be seen as inappropriate. This shall leave the child undecided and feel confused as he has no idea why both parents liked his behavior at the first time and punished him at the second time. This method results in an undecided hesitant person who when he grows up and gets married would treat his wife gently and affectionately at some times and the opposite at other times for no reason for such oscillation.
7. **Arousal of psychological pain:** This is done through making the child feel guilty whenever he commits an undesired behavior. This includes belittling and humiliating the child. This makes the child lose self-confidence and result in an introverted, withdrawn personality which directs aggression towards destroying himself. In the activity room, if the teacher once asks a question, the child may feel scared even if he knows the correct answer, for fear of being wrong and thus will be ridiculed.
8. **Discrimination:** It is defined as deliberate inequality between all children and showing preference for one over the other due to gender or the order of the children. This creates a malevolent selfish personality which is used to taking without giving, which likes to possess everything at the expense of others.

Contemporary educational methods in raising children:

A lot of important contemporary educational methods are adopted, including:

1. Method of dialogue: Set aside time to sit with your child away from television, teach him how to communicate with others, and before that teach him how to express his opinion clearly and politely. Make of yourself an example for your children. This is the shortest cut to implant positive concepts in themselves. Dialogue protects our children from many problems such as sexual harassment, and this was confirmed by a study Hala Al-Balushi (2015) and another by Yamana Trikeh (2016) who shed light on the importance of educating mothers about their role in educating their children and training them to use parenting skills in protecting their children. This is because the family is primarily responsible for protecting its children.
2. Balance method: Balance between your children's psychological, physical and mental needs, and develop all of these aspects in them with no excess or negligence. Assist them with balancing their demands and desires, foods and drinks, getting children's stories and studying them, and guide them to look after their teeth and hygiene. A study by Carreteiro, Rui Manuel (2016) confirms that a strong relationship between raising children through to be readers and understanding sentences and grammar and enjoying reading has been observed.
3. Motivation: Support your child's self-confidence as it is the key to his adaptability with the various circumstances and hardships. Stimulate him to speak before adults, and whatever the concerns and circumstances, remember to give him a small gift when he acts in a positive and distinctive behavior. Muhammad Abdulaziz Al-Taleb (2012) confirms that the family environment that supports the growth of talents perceived by gifted students enjoy a high level of significance in its overall degree and dimensions. This means that motivation and a supportive environment have the greatest impact on the achievement of gifted children.
4. Lack of distraction while caring for children: Children do not need attention from their parents all the time, but when they are with them, they should not be busy doing any other tasks and therefore a need to focus on spending a good time with them is necessary. Amongst the things that parents should avoid doing when they are around with their children include being busy checking the email, spending time on social media, or being busy using the smartphone. Such behaviors negatively affect children and make them feel that their parents do not communicate with them as required.

Ali Rashid (2018) provides guidelines for parents for the proper dealing with the child:

1. We must deal well with children calmly, away from any emotion or haste.
2. Your child's behavior is a reflection of your behavior, so parents should be fully aware of their own behavior, as children acquire the behaviors of their parents significantly.
3. The child is like a malleable, dough-like mass that can be shaped as we like, so we have to shape it as best as possible.
4. The pressures of life are communicated to the children, whether at home, in kindergarten, and with friends, so parents should not be a new source of these pressures.
5. The child's conversations should not be ignored, even if he is stuttering. His feelings, both sad and happy, must be shared, and his desires must be met as much as possible with love and without violence.
6. Give your child tenderness, love and care, because depriving him of that makes him suffer from a weak ability to concentrate and lack of attention, which makes him rush to behaviors without thinking, and he commits mistakes, and thus causes harm to those around him.
7. We all love our children, and we hope that they grow up in the best way, but this is not a justification for cruelty against them in order to make them the person we like, and ignore their desires. All we have to do is help them discover themselves to reach what is best for them.
8. Encouraging children's sense of ownership by parents, without exaggeration, helps to instill positive attitudes towards these children's respect for the ownership of others, and to develop in themselves positive values and behavioral attitudes towards integrity. Also, we must respect the rights of the child with regard to the tools, toys and books he has, and leave him free to act in case it is acceptable.

We must realize that among the most important motives that drive a child to steal are the following: ignorance, deprivation, revenge, getting rid of a problem, a desire to obtain a prominent position, imitating peers, spending free time, satisfying an attitude, proving oneself, and suffering from a mental illness.

9. A child who lives in an environment that does not help to develop the value of honesty can fall prey to telling lies just like an imaginative child who can also tell lies. A child who fears punishment lies, and a child who wants to have a place among his peers, he may practice lying. We thus need to find out whether lying is a symptom or a frequent behavior, bearing in mind that neither punishment nor threat can be the solution to treat lying. Rather, treatment begins from the environment in which the child lives that should treat him well. Therefore, the environment should be tolerant, and contributes to fulfilling the child's psychological and environmental needs.

10. A child's stubbornness may showcase physical fatigue, psychological distress, feeling of insignificance, or a desire for independence. Among the methods of treating the child's stubbornness are: not to over-issue orders, taking into account the age that the child is going through, and also to satisfy the child's needs in a proper manner, to avoid making the child orders or instructions as much as possible. Thus, exercising parental authority in the form of dialogue and understanding is highly desired.

11. Among the most important causes of a child's nervousness are the following:

- Inherited aspects in personality, physical causes, parental nervousness, excessive stress of parents, excessive pampering, negligence of the child's needs to play, excessive parental anxiety, neglecting the child's needs and tendencies, family disintegration, and jealousy among siblings.

To treat a child's nervousness, the following needs to be done:

- Creating a calm and serene home environment and minimize parental authority.

- Not reacting in a nervous way to the child's sense of nervousness

- Showing for that child we understand his nervousness.

- Giving the child opportunities to express what is bothering him, for the child to get used to using dialogue instead of heated emotions.

- Creating an organized life for him.

12. The shy child suffers from his inability to take and give, and he influences introversion and daydreaming. He also suffers from lack of self-confidence, as well as the agony of loneliness, as he is unable to mingle with life relationships. He also does not learn from his experiences, and always feels inferior and imperfection.

Shyness could be ascribed to being the only child or the child leads a soft life different that he cannot find outside, excessive pampering and abnormal relationships with his parents, suffering from some disability, or being low-achiever at school

In order to treat shyness, the child must be given confident, and thus feels loved and respected. Also, creating a safe atmosphere in the family and not entrusting tasks that go beyond his competencies and, training the child to make friends, and utilizing independent education are some other common ways.

Research tools:

The open-question individual interview questionnaire

Description of the form:

The tool consists of a set of dimensions, and each dimension contains a set of open-ended questions focusing on the following age stages:

1. The prenatal stage (starts from fertilization until birth).
2. Infancy or breastfeeding stage (includes the first two years of a child's life).
3. Early childhood stage, divided into two sub-stages:

A. The nursery stage (and it includes from 2-4) years.

B. Kindergarten stage (it includes 4-6 years).

The mother gets one mark if her answer is not satisfactory, but if her answer is simple, she gets two marks, and if her response is conscious, she gets 3 marks.

The questions were asked in a colloquial manner due to the lack of education and thus the inability to understand some of the question terminology in the classical language.

Homogeneity among the sample members in terms of chronological age

Table (1)

Homogeneity among the control group members in terms of chronological age

N = 40

Variables	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	chi-Square Test	Level of Significance	Significance
Chronological age	29.47	4.17	17.00	.256	insignificant

It is obvious from Table (1) that there exist no statistically significant differences between the sample members in terms of chronological age, which indicates the homogeneity of the sample members.

Equating both the experimental and control groups in terms of the mothers' awareness questionnaire:

The researcher found the significance of the differences between the mean scores of the members of the experimental and control groups in the pre-measurement on the mothers' awareness questionnaire as shown in Table (1)

The standardized open-question individual interview questionnaire: the researcher felt a need to prepare the standardized open-question individual interview questionnaire for rural mothers. The form includes the following dimensions (prenatal stage - the infancy stage - the nursery stage - the kindergarten stage). These dimensions were selected based on past literature that emphasize that personality of the child is shaped by 70%

in the first six years and this is confirmed by Khaled Salah Hanafi (2016). This proves that the early childhood stage is what shapes the personality of the child, as indicated by Nabil Saad Khalil Gerges (1997).

The objective of the standardized open-question individual interview questionnaire

The researcher prepared this tool for the purpose of employing it in measuring the degree of rural mothers' awareness in the following stages (the prenatal stage- the infancy stage - the nursery stage - the kindergarten stage). This form is employed in the pre, post and follow-up evaluation. Also, to the best knowledge of the researcher, there is a scarcity in the tools to be used for measuring proper parenting methods in these stages.

Preparation steps of the standardized open-question individual interview questionnaire for rural mothers.

The researcher went through the following procedures during designing the form:

First: Creating the form.

Second: Initial testing of the form

Third: Verifying the psychometric properties of the questionnaire.

Fourth: The final version of the form.

Also, the researcher was keen on ensuring the psychometric properties of the standardized open-question individual interview questionnaire for rural mothers

The validity, consistency and internal consistency of the form in its initial form were verified as follows:

1. Form validity:

- A. Factorial validity: To measure the factorial validity of the form, the researcher employed the Exploratory Factor Analysis by the Principal Components Method with rotating the axes using the Varimax Method. The researcher also used Bartlett's Test of Sphericity to ensure that the correlation matrix is not equal to the unit matrix. (Field, A, 2009, P648). It was found that the result of Bartlett's Test was statistically significant at (0.01). This indicates that the correlation matrix has no complete correlation coefficients, which means that the correlation matrix is not equal to the unit matrix and that there is a correlation between some variables in the matrix which provides a statistically sound basis for using factor analysis method. The researcher calculated the following:

* Matrix of correlations of direct education dimensions list

* Loading of items and dimensions of direct education list based on the five factors resulting from the factor analysis before rotating.

* Loading of items and dimensions of direct education list based on the five factors resulting from the factor analysis after rotating.

The following table shows a matrix of correlation coefficients among the form dimensions:

Table (2)

Matrix of correlation coefficients among dimensions of the standardized open-question individual interview questionnaire for rural mothers

Dimensions	1	2	3	4
Prenatal stage	---	**0.605	**0.605	**0.586
Infancy stage	**0.653	---	0.586	**0.570
Nursery stage	**0.612	**0.586	---	-**0.669
Kindergarten Stage	**0.605	**0.570	**0.669	---

The following table illustrates the loadings of form items with regard to the four factors resulting from the factor analysis before rotation.

Table (3)

Loadings items and dimensions of the standardized open-question individual interview questionnaire for rural mothers with regard to the four factors resulting from the factor analysis before rotation.

Item	Loading of First Factor	Loading of Second Factor	Loading of Third Factor	Loading of Fourth Factor
1	0.412			
2	0.436			
3	0.408			
4		0.480		
5		0.469		
6		0.470		

7		0.444	
8		0.420	
9		0.417	
10			0.449
11			0.406
12			0.455
Factors/ Dimensions		Eigen Value	Explained variance ratio %
Prenatal stage		2.065	62.32
infancy stage		1.941	60.59
Nursery stage		1.878	59.60
Kindergarten stage		1.777	58.14

According to Guttman-Kaiser Criterion, the Eigen Value which explains the value of the total variance should be greater than one (Marques, J, 2007, 339). Accordingly, the previous table shows that there exists one factor that explains the total variance after ignoring the other factors as their Eigen values are less than one. Thus, it can be said that factor analysis revealed five factors that explain the variance of rural mothers' performance with regard to the form.

Also, the value of the acceptable and statistically significant loading must not be less than (0.30); accordingly, it is evident from the previous table that the dimensions of the form showed loadings whose value exceeded (0.30) on the single factor. Thus, such loadings are statistically significant. (Saud bin Dhahyan and Izzat Abdul Hamid, 2002, 206)

The following table also illustrates the loadings of the form items with regard to the four factors resulting from the factor analysis after rotation.

Table (4)

Loadings of the form items and dimensions on the four factors resulting from the factor analysis after rotation

Item	Loading of first factor	Loading of second factor	Loading of third factor	Loading of fourth factor
1	0.406			
2	0.421			
3	0.396			
4		0.474		
5		0.461		
6		0.463		
7			0.432	
8			0.413	
9			0.410	
10				0.433
11				0.397
12				0.441
factors/dimensions		Eigen value	Explained variance ratio %	
Prenatal stage		2.021	61.05	
Infancy stage		1.929	69.11	
Nursery stage		1.850	58.47	
Kindergarten stage		1.762	57.09	

Through calculating the factorial validity, it is evident that the form enjoys an acceptable coefficient of validity which indicates the possibility of using it in the current research and guarantee reliability of the results concluded.

2. Questionnaire reliability

1. Cronbach's alpha

Using the Cronbach's alpha, the researcher verified the reliability of the form. The following table illustrates the values of the reliability coefficients by the Cronbach's alpha for each item and the reliability factor as a whole.

Table (5)

Values of the reliability coefficients of "Cronbach's alpha" for each item and the reliability factor of the standardized open-question individual interview questionnaire for rural mothers as a whole

Item	Cronbach's alpha Coefficients	Item	Cronbach's alpha Coefficients
1	0.716	7	0.738
2	0.739	8	0.740
3	0.716	9	0.746
4	0.750	10	0.750
5	0.731	11	0.741
6	0.751	12	0.744
Reliability coefficients of the form as a whole 0.771			

If the Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient for each question of the form is less than the Cronbach's alpha value of the total score of the questions of the list as a whole given in the table, this means that the question is important and in case it is eliminated from the list negatively affects it. If the Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient for each question is greater than or equal to the Cronbach's alpha value of the whole form in the table, this means that the presence of the question reduces or weakens the reliability of the questionnaire (Ahmed Ghoneim and Nasr Sabry, 2000, 188).

According to the previous table, the reliability coefficients of the questionnaire items is less than the value of reliability coefficients of the whole list, which scores (0.771).

C. Internal consistency of standardized open-question individual interview questionnaire for rural mothers as a whole:

1. The internal consistency of the questionnaire's items through calculating the correlation coefficient between the score of each item and the total score of the form. The following table shows the correlation coefficient between the score of each item and the total score of the form

Table (6)

Correlation coefficients between the score of each item of the form and the total score of the form

Item	Correlation coefficients	Item	Correlation coefficients
1	0.702	7	0.709
2	0.706	8	0.682
3	0.698	9	0.681
4	0.710	10	0.674
5	0.694	11	0.690
6	0.700	12	0.667

Correlation coefficients between the score of each item and the total score of the dimension; results are shown in the following table:

Table (7): Correlation coefficients between the score of each item and the total score of the dimension

Item	Correlation Coefficient	Item	Correlation Coefficient
1	0.733	7	0.731
2	0.739	8	0.706
3	0.729	9	0.705
4	0.741	10	0.697
5	0.728	11	0.716
6	0.732	12	0.695

2. The internal consistency of the questionnaire's dimensions through calculating the correlation coefficient between the total score of each dimension and the total score of the form. Results are shown in the following table.

Table (8): Correlation coefficients between the total score of each dimension and the total score of the form:

No.	Dimensions	Correlation Coefficient
1	Prenatal stage	**0.798
2	Infancy stage	**0.786
3	Nursery stage	**0.780
4	Kindergarten stage	**0.794

In accordance with the previous table, the correlation coefficients between the total score for each dimension and the score of the questionnaire are statistically significant at (0.01). Through the data provided, the internal consistency of the questionnaire's vocabulary and dimensions is obvious. This indicates the possibility of employing it in the current research, and guarantees the results to be concluded by the research.

Pilot study:

The researcher conducted an initial pilot experiment on a sample of fifteen rural mothers residing Mandara Village in Fayoum Governorate to explore the suitability of the questionnaire and the program in terms of appropriate formulation of items for mothers. By doing so, the researcher aimed to verify the validity and reliability of the measures, and to determine the time required to implement the form and carry out the proposed program. The pilot study revealed a lack of mothers' knowledge of the proper parenting methods of their children. Mothers raise their children as they have been raised by beating, cruelty, nervousness, and oppression, and obliging them to shoulder burdens beyond their capabilities, without identifying the characteristics of the child's development and with no knowledge of the contemporary modern methods of parenting.

Foundations for preparing the proposed program:

The nature of the research sample affects in a large way the process of program preparation and implementation, as the knowledge characteristics of rural mothers are an important factor in their awareness. In light of the framework of past literature and the prepared theoretical framework in addition to the strategies of dialogue, discussion, lecturing and acting scenes, and to answer the research question "What is the effectiveness of a program for rural mothers to develop their awareness about proper parenting methods for their children from birth to early childhood stage? ", the requirements for the proposed program were specified as follows below; identifying the growth characteristics of each stage in the child's life since prenatal stage with its requirements and needs towards the infancy stage and the preschool stage. Also, an inquiry about the wrong methods that mothers use in parenting, and the proper methods that the mother should adopt in raising her children was probed. The program consists of (16) sessions, with two sessions per week basis over a period of two months. The duration of each session ranges from one and a half hours to two hours. During that time, a lecture along with dialogue, discussion, acting situations and watching some various videos are presented with the purpose of developing awareness among rural mothers of proper parenting methods.

Study Results:

Results of the first hypothesis:

There exist statistically significant differences between the mean scores of the research sample's scores for the two groups: control and experimental in the post application in the standardized open-question individual interview questionnaire for rural mothers to measure their awareness of the proper parenting methods in favour of the experimental group

To verify the validity of the hypothesis, the researcher employed the Mann Whitney Test to find the differences between the mean scores of the children of the experimental and control groups.

Table (9)

The significance of the differences between the mean scores of the experimental and control groups in the post-measurement on the interview questionnaire

N = 40

Measure Dimensions	Control Group N= (20)		Experimental Group N= (20)		(z) Value	Significance Level	Result
	mean score of ranks	Total score of ranks	mean score of ranks	Total score of ranks			

1. Prenatal stage	10.50	210	30.50	610	5.71	.001	Significant
2. Infancy stage	10.50	210	30.50	610	5.72	.001	Significant
3. Nursery stage	10.50	210	30.50	610	5.66	.001	Significant
4. Kindergarten stage	10.50	210	30.50	610	5.71	.001	Significant
5. Total score	10.50	210	30.50	610	5.48	.001	Significant

Based on the previous table, there exist statistically significant differences at .01 among the mean scores of mothers of the experimental group and the control group on the interview questionnaire in the post-measurement in favor of the experimental group.

The following graph illustrates the differences between the two groups in the post-measurement, as it shows the low level of awareness ranks of rural mothers, i.e. the control group. However, there is an obvious increase in the ranks of the degrees of awareness of rural mothers in the experimental group in the post-test, which has a great impact on the importance of the program used and therefore the first hypothesis can be accepted.

Figure (1) shows the significance of the difference between the mean ranks of mothers' scores for the experimental and control group in the post measurement

الدرجة الكلية: total score

رياض الاطفال: Kindergarten

الحضانه: Nursery

المهده: Infancy

المرحلة الجنينية: Prenatal stage

The second hypothesis

There exist statistically significant differences between the mean scores of the experimental group scores in the two applications (pre and post) in the standardized open-question individual interview questionnaire for rural mothers to measure their awareness of proper parenting methods in favor of the post application.

To verify the validity of this hypothesis, the researcher used the Wilcoxon test to find the differences between the mean scores of the experimental group's children's scores in the two applications, pre and post, to apply the program to the interview form as shown in Table (10)

Table (10)

Variables	measurement pre – post	number	mean score of ranks	total score of ranks	Z	significance	direction of significance
Prenatal	negative ranks	-	-	-	3.95	significant at 0.01	in favour of the post-measurement
	positive ranks	20	10.50	210			
	equal ranks	-	-	-			
	total	20	-	-			

Infancy stage	negative ranks	-	-	-	3.97	significant at 0.01	in favour of the post-measurement
	positive ranks	20	10.50	210			
	equal ranks	-					
	total	20					
Nursery stage	negative ranks	-	-	-	3.95	significant at 0.01	in favour of the post-measurement
	positive ranks	20	10.50	210			
	equal ranks	-					
	total	20					
Kindergarten stage	negative ranks	-	-	-	3.97	significant at 0.01	in favour of the post-measurement
	positive ranks	20	10.50	210			
	equal ranks	-					
	total	20					
the measure as a whole	negative ranks	-	-	-	3.94	significant at 0.01	in favour of the post-measurement
	positive ranks	20	10.50	210			
	equal ranks	-					
	total	20					

Z=2.58 at 0.01 Z=1.96 at 0.01

Table (10) illustrates that there exist statistically significant differences at 0.01 between the mean scores of mothers' ranks in the pre and post measurements to apply the program to the interview questionnaire (prenatal stage – infancy - nursery - kindergarten and total score).

The following graph shows the differences between the mean scores of mothers' ranks in the pre and post measurements

A graph showing the differences between the mean scores of mothers' ranks in the pre and post measurements

الدرجة الكلية: total score

رياض الأطفال: Kindergarten

الحضانة: Nursery

المهد: Infancy

المرحلة الجنينية: Prenatal stage

بعدي post

قبلي pre

The third hypothesis:

There exist statistically significant differences between the mean scores of rural mothers in the two measurements (post and tracer) for applying the standardized individual interview questionnaire for rural mothers to measure their awareness of proper parenting methods in favor of the follow-up measurement.

To verify the validity of that hypothesis, the researcher used the Wilcoxon test to find the differences between the mean scores of the mothers' scores in the experimental group in the post and tracer applications to apply the program to the interview questionnaire as shown in Table (11)

Table (11)

The differences between the mean scores of the experimental group's children's scores in the post and follow-up applications of the program on the interview questionnaire using Wilcoxon's test (n = 20)

Variables	measurement pre – post	Number	Mean score of ranks	Total score of ranks	Z	Significance	direction of significance
Prenatal stage	negative ranks	-	-	-	2.71	significant at 0.01	in favour of the follow-up measure
	positive ranks	8	4.50	36.00			
	equal ranks	12					
	total	20					
Infancy stage	negative ranks	-	-	-	2.07	significant at 0.05	in favour of the follow-up measure
	positive ranks	5	3.00	15.00			
	equal ranks	15					
	total	20					
Nursery stage	negative ranks	-	-	-	2.39	significant at 0.05	in favour of the follow-up measure
	positive ranks	7	4.00	28.00			
	equal ranks	13					
	total	20					
Kindergarten stage	negative ranks	-	-	-	2.12	significant at 0.05	in favour of the follow-up measure
	positive ranks	5	3.00	15.00			
	equal ranks	15					
	total	20					
the measure as a whole	negative ranks	-	-	-	3.65	significant at 0.01	in favour of the follow-up measure
	positive ranks	17	9.00	153.00			
	equal ranks	3					
	total	20					

Z=2.58 at 0.01 Z=1.96 at 0.05

Based on Table (11), there exist statistically significant differences at 0.01 between the mean scores of the mothers' ranks in the post and tracer measurements for the application of the program on the interview form (the prenatal stage and the total score) in favour of the follow-up measurement.

However, there exist statistically significant differences at 0.05 between the mean scores of mothers' ranks in the post and follow-up measurements for the application of the program on the mothers' awareness form (infancy - nursery - kindergarten). The researcher provided mothers with a summary that supports proper parenting as well as answers to mothers' questions, which was published in a study by Hutchings (2018).

Discussion and interpretation of results:

Based on the previous results that the proposed program has contributed to raising awareness among rural mothers of the proper methods of parenting, as the difference between the mean score of ranks of the experimental and control group scores in the post-measurement was statistically significant in favor of the post application, which indicates the effectiveness of the proposed program and the methods of proper parenting methods it offers. The program was based on a set of strategies suitable for rural mothers, such as dialogue, discussion, lecture, displaying some videos of proper and wrong methods of parenting and commenting on them. The activities of the program helped mothers interact with the content presented to them, give them good practical experiences, where a supportive environment full of love, friendliness and mutual understanding between mothers and the researcher was created. This contributed to their participation in implementing the program in a positive way, and the researcher emphasized the mothers' cooperation while thinking about clarifying solutions to the problems they encounter while raising their children and correcting their behavior with their children.

Study recommendations:

Based on the results of the study, the researcher recommends the following:

- Establishing an educational pharmacy inside the kindergarten through educational consultations and responses in order to serve as a helping hand for the mother to solve her problems with her children, and thus we will bridge the gap between the house and the kindergarten.
- Providing educational courses for mothers within the kindergarten to identify their mistakes in education.

- Mothers should provide sufficient quality time with the child and listen to their complaints and discuss them.
- Paying attention to a bedtime story, kissing and cuddling before going to bed are crucial.
- The enjoyment of raising children should be available to the mother in order to relieve her of the burden of parenting, and to feel the pleasure during raising her children. .
- Allocating time to play with the child, even once a week.

Study recommendations:

In light of the findings of the study, the researcher done research in the following themes:

- The effectiveness of a program based on social play to develop self-confidence among kindergarten children in the countryside.
- Positive parenting of kindergarten children in rural areas and its role in building an independent personality.
- The effectiveness of a program to treat the impact of the use of corporal punishment on the personality of the rural child.

References:

First: Arabic references

- Musa Naguib Musa: The Concept of Methods of Parenting with Children, 2013, Aluka Network, a Comprehensive Islamic, Intellectual and Cultural Network
- Abdul Karim Mahmoud Saleh: Journal of the College of Basic Education, University of Babylon, Issue 15, 2014.
- Human Rights Council: Twenty-second session, United Nations, final study submitted by the Human Rights Council Advisory Committee on rural women and the right to food, 2012.
- Samah Abadeh, Rural Women, Products of Life and Food, Forgotten Toilers, Article, 2015.
- Muhammad Abdel Aziz Al-Taleb: The family environment that supports the growth of talent as perceived by gifted students and its relationship with some demographic variables, The Arab Journal for the Development of Excellence, Issue 5, 2012.
- Nabil El-Sayed Hassan: The Impact of the Virtual Electronic Environment on Positive Thinking in Children, The First International Conference of Faculty of Education for Early Childhood - Assiut University, Issue 1, 2018.
- Gamal Ali Al-Dahshan: Raising the Egyptian Child in the Digital Age between Real Challenges and Future Ambitions, The First International Conference of Faculty of Education for Early Childhood - Assiut University, 2018 AD.
- Hala Al-Balushi: Modern strategies to face the psychological effects of sexual harassment. Reading Therapy, The Second International Conference on Child Protection from Sexual Harassment, Dubai, 2015.
- Yamna Traykeh: The Family's Role in Protecting Children from Violence, Allam Al-Tarbiya Journal, Egypt, Issue 54, 2016.
- Ali Rashid: The Art of Dealing with Children, The First International Conference of Faculty of Education for Early Childhood - Assiut University, 2018.
- Khaled Salah Hanafi: The Evolution of Preschool Child Education between Present and Application, 2016, Faculty of Education, Alexandria University.
- Qasim, Insaf Abdo (2004), Women and Development in Yemen, National Information Center.
- Al-Zoghbi, Salah El-Din Mahmoud and Mustafa Kamel Mohamed Al-Sayed, 1995 The necessary institutional changes to support rural community development in Egypt (Health Organization), Volume Three, Academy of Research, Scientific and Technology, Food and Agricultural Research Council, Faculty of Agriculture, Alexandria University
- Hegazi, Ahmed Magdy and Khalil Abdel-Maqsood, 2005 The Families of Female Heads of Household in Fayoum Governorate, A Social Field Study, Al-Omraneya Press, Giza, First Edition.
- Nabil Saad Khalil Gerges: Journal of Educational and Social Studies. Faculty of Education - Helwan University. Third volume. Second Issue - June 1997.
- Ahmad Al-Rifai Ghoneim and Nasr Mahmoud Sabry (2000). Statistical analysis of data using (SPSS) software. Cairo: Quba Publishing House.
- Osama Rabie (2007). Statistical analysis using SPSS software. Cairo: The Academic Library.
- Samia Al-Ansari (2006). Educational Psychology. Alexandria: University Knowledge House.
- Saad Zaghoul Bashir (2003). Your guide to SPSS. Iraq, Baghdad: Publications of the Arab Institute for Training and Research in Statistics.
- Safwat Ahmed Farag (1991). Factor analysis in the behavioral sciences. I (2), Cairo: The Anglo-Egyptian Library.
- Salah al-Din Mahmoud Allam (2000). Educational and psychological measurement and evaluation, its basics, applications and contemporary trends. Cairo: Dar Al-Fekr Al-Araby.

- Salah Murad (2011). *Statistical methods in psychological, educational and social sciences*. Cairo: The Anglo-Egyptian Library.
- Saud Bin Dhahyan and Ezzat Abdul Hamid (2002), *Data Processing Using SPSS, Part Two, Book Four, Systematic Research Series*, Riyadh: King Fahd National Library.

Second: Foreign references

- Johnston, P; Wilkinson, K (2009). Enhancing Validity of Critical Tasks Selected for College and University Program Portfolios. **National Forum of Teacher Education Journal**, (19) 3, PP1-6.
- Field, A. (2009). **Discovering Statistics Using SPSS**, Third Edition, London :SAGE Publications Ltd.
- Johnston, P; Wilkinson, K (2009). Enhancing Validity of Critical Tasks Selected for College and University Program Portfolios. *National Forum of Teacher Education Journal*, (19) 3, PP1-6.
- Field, A. (2009). *Discovering Statistics Using SPSS*, Third Edition, London: SAGE Publications Ltd.
- Child Physical Punishment, Parenting, and School Readiness Weegar, Kelly; Guérin-Marion, Camille; Fréchette, Sabrina; Romano, Elisa *Infant and Child Development*, v27 n1 Jan-Feb 2018 Available on (ERIC Number: EJ1168553)
- Family Context Assessment and Positive Parenting Policies Barreto, Florencia Belén; González Safont, Lúcia; Roncallo, Claudia Patricia; Acha, Joana; Sánchez de Miguel, Manuel *Early Child Development and Care*, v188 n11 p1605-1618 2018 Available on (ERIC Number: EJ1191778)
- Relations among Intimate Partner Violence, Maternal Depressive Symptoms, and Maternal Parenting Behaviors Gustafsson, Hanna C.; Cox, Martha J., *Journal of Marriage and Family*, v74 n5 p1005-1020 Oct 2012, Available on (ERIC Number: EJ990582)
- Relations among Intimate Partner Violence, Maternal Depressive Symptoms, and Maternal Parenting Behaviors. Gustafsson, Hanna C.; Cox, Martha J., *Journal of Marriage and Family*, v74 n5 p1005-1020 Oct 2012, Available on (ERIC Number: EJ990582)
- Long-Term Effects of Stressors on Relationship Well-Being and Parenting among Rural African American Women Murry, Velma M.; Harrell, Amanda W.; Brody, Gene H.; Chen, Yi-Fu; Simons, Ronald L.; Black, Angela R.; Cutrona, Carolyn E.; Gibbons, Frederick X. *Family Relations*, v57 n2 p117-127 Apr 2008 Available on (ERIC Number: EJ789849)
- Positive Parenting Support during Family Reunification Balsells Bailón, M. A.; Mateos Inchaurredo, A.; Urrea Monclús, A.; Vaquero Tió, E. *Early Child Development and Care*, v188 n11 p1566-1578 2018, Available on (ERIC Number: EJ1191777)
- Parenting Gifted Children: Voices from India Sharma, Jyoti; Bagai, Shobha; Tyagi, Pankaj; Biswal, Bibhu *Parenting for High Potential*, v7 n4 p24-26 Dec 2018 Available on (ERIC Number: EJ1199567)
- Parenting for Competence and Parenting with Competence: Essential Connections between Parenting and Social and Emotional Learning Miller, Jennifer S.; Wanless, Shannon B.; Weissberg, Roger P. *School Community Journal*, v28 n2 p9-28 2018, Available on (ERIC Number: EJ1201828)
- The Reach up Early Childhood Parenting Program: Origins, Content, and Implementation Walker, Susan P.; Chang, Susan M.; Smith, Joanne A.; Baker-Henningham, Helen, *ZERO TO THREE*, v38 n4 p37-43 Mar 2018, Available on (ERIC Number: EJ1174111)
- Web-Based Parenting Support: Development of the COPING Confident Parenting Programme Hutchings, Judith; Owen, Dawn; Williams, Margiad *Education Sciences*, v8 Article 59 2018, Available on (ERIC Number: EJ1199438)
- An Online Parenting Program Grows Digital Parenting Skills and Parent-School Connection Clarkson, Anne; Zierl, Lori, *Journal of Extension*, v56 n5 Article 5RIB1 Sep 2018, Available on (ERIC Number: EJ1192081)
- Reading Processes and Parenting Styles Carreteiro, Rui Manuel; Justo, João Manuel; Figueira, Ana Paula *Journal of Psycholinguistic Research*, v45 n4 p901-914 Aug 2016, Available on (ERIC Number: : EJ1115986)
- Modern Parenthood as a Subject of Research Polivanova, K. N. *Russian Education & Society*, v60 n4 p334-347 2018, Available on (ERIC Number: : EJ1183377).

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